

Allelism between blast (BI) resistance genes *Pi-4a(t)* and *Pi-ta*

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Twenty-two near-isogenic lines (NILs) carrying single genes for complete resistance to BI were previously developed at IRRI. The recurrent parent was the highly susceptible indica cultivar CO 39. The donor parents were the resistant indica cultivars Tetep and 5173 and japonica cultivars Pai-kan-tao and LAC23. NILs were divided into six groups based on their reaction patterns to IRRI test isolates. The resistance gene in C101PKT, one of the NILs belonging to group III, was designated *Pi-4a(t)*. We found that *Pi-4a(t)* was identical to the

known BI resistance locus *Pi-ta*. All of the NILs in group III were shown to carry *Pi-ta*.

To compare resistance genes in the NILs with previously described BI resistance loci, we conducted allelism tests between C101PKT and Kiyosawa's differentials (KDs), a set of cultivars carrying 12 known resistance genes. We also conducted allelism tests between NILs belonging to group III and KDs.

Seedlings of parental lines and F₂ plants were grown in a greenhouse and inoculated at the fifth- to sixth-leaf stage by spraying with an aqueous spore suspension of 5 × 10⁴ conidia/ml. The pathogen isolates used for developing the NILs, IK81-3 (101), IK81-25 (102), and 43 (105), were also used in these experiments. Disease reactions were scored about 7 d after inoculation.

Table 1. Reaction of parental lines and F₂ populations to isolate IK81-3 (101).

Parental line and F ₂ population	Reaction to IK81-3 ^a			Goodness of fit	
	R	S	Total	Ratio	χ ²
CO 39 (S line)	0	19	19		
C101PKT [<i>Pi-4a(t)</i>]	20	0	20		
F ₂ CO 39/C101PKT	91	31	122	3:1	0.01 ns
104PKT (S line)	0	18	18		
K 1 (<i>Pi-ta</i>)	12	0	12		
F ₂ K 1/C104PKT	177	44	221	3:1	3.05 ns
C104PKT (S line)	0	17	17		
Pi No. 4 (<i>Pi-ta</i> ²)	16	0	16		
F ₂ Pi No. 4/C104PKT	143	39	182	3:1	1.24 ns
Crosses with NILs in group III					
F ₂ K 1/					
C101PKT	420	0	420	1:0	
C101TTP-1	408	0	408	1:0	
C101TTP-2	413	0	413	1:0	
C101TTP-3	—	—	—	—	
C101TTP-4	236	0	236	1:0	
C101TTP-6	441	0	441	1:0	
C102TTP ^b	192	0	192	1:0	
C105TTP-1 ^c	201	0	201	1:0	
C105TTP-2L23 ^c	119	0	110	1:0	
C105TTP-4L6 ^c	216	0	216	1:0	
F ₂ Pi No. 4/					
C101PKT	392	0	392	1:0	
C101TTP-1	221	—	221	1:0	
C101TTP-2	201	0	201	1:0	
C101TTP-3	107	0	107	1:0	
C101TTP-4	220	0	220	1:0	
C101TTP-6	214	0	214	1:0	
C102TTP ^b	206	0	206	1:0	
C105TTP-1	220	0	220	1:0	
C105TTP-2L23	179	0	179	1:0	
C105TTP-4L6	—	—	—	—	

R = resistant, S = susceptible. ^aIsolate IK81-25 (102) was inoculated. ^cIsolate 43 (105) was inoculated.

Table 2. Reaction pattern of K 1, Pi No. 4, and NILs belonging to group III.^a

Line	Test isolates ^b				
	101	102	103	104	105
Kiyosawa's differentials					
K 1 (<i>Pi-ta</i>)	R	R	S	S	R
Pi No. 4 (<i>Pi-ta</i> ²)	R	R	R	R	R
NILs in group III					
C101PKT [<i>Pi-4a(t)</i>]	R	R	S	S	R
C101TTP-1	R	R	S	S	R
C101TTP-2	R	R	S	S	R
C101TTP-3	R	R	S	S	R
C101TTP-4	R	R	S	S	R
C101TTP-6	R	R	S	S	R
C102TTP	R	R	S	S	R
C105TTP-1	R	R	S	S	R
C105TTP-2L23	R	R	S	S	R
C105TTP-4L6	R	R	S	S	R

^aR = resistant, S = susceptible. ^b101 = IK81-3, 102 = IK81-25, 103 = PO6-6, 104 = PO3-82-51, 105 = 43

None of NILs in group III gave susceptible recombinants in the crosses with K 1 (*Pi-ta*) and Pi No. 4 (*Pi-ta*²) at the F₂ generation (Table 1). These results showed that resistance genes in K 1, Pi No. 4, and the NILs in group III are allelic or closely linked. Both K 1 and Pi No. 4 have resistance genes at the *Pi-ta* locus, and it has been reported that Pai-kan-tao (the donor parent of C101PKT) has *Pi-ta*. The reaction pattern of C101PKT and other NILs in group III to five IRRI test isolates was the same as for that of K 1 (*Pi-ta*) (Table 2). These results indicate that *Pi-4a(t)* was identical to *Pi-ta*, and that all of the NILs in group III have *Pi-ta*. ■

Characterization of weakly virulent bacterial strains associated with rice bacterial blight (BB) or leaf streak (BLS) in southern India

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We classified 70 Indian strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (*Xoo*) from major rice-growing areas in India

into races and six serological groups on the basis of their reactivity to a panel of six monoclonal antibodies (mAbs). We retested with a high-titer clone of mAb *Xco-1* and found that the strains of serogroups V and VII (which did not react earlier) gave very weak to moderate

Table 1. Serological classification of 87 Indian strains of *Xoo* with monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) and reactions with *Xoor* and T mAbs.

mAb	Serological group of <i>Xoo</i>			<i>Xoor</i>
	I	II	V	
<i>X1</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>Xco-1</i>	+	+	-	-
<i>Xco-2</i>	+	-	-	-
<i>Xco-5</i>	-	-	-	-
<i>Xco-T</i> (225)	-	-	+ ^a	+
<i>Xco-T</i> (226)	-	-	+	-
<i>Xccola</i>	-	-	-	+
Strains (no.)	67	18	2 ^b	8

^a*Xoo* strain PXO86 (serogroup I) and USA strain X1-5 (serogroup III) showed positive reactions with the mAb. ^bT strains (T1, T2).

Table 2. Phenotypic characteristics of *Xoo*, *Xoor*, and weakly virulent bacterial strains from rice in India.

Phenotypic characteristic (17 strains)	<i>Xoo</i> (8 strains)	<i>Xoor</i> (8 strains)	T1, T2
Acetoin production	-	-	-
Growth on L-alanine	- ^a	+	+
Growth in presence of cupric nitrate (0.001%)	-	-	+
Growth on vitamin-free casamino-acid (0.2%)	- ^a	+	+
β-glucosidase production	+	+	+
Phenylalanine deaminase production	- ^a	+	-
Tyrosinase production	- ^a	-	+

^aStrain X1-5, a strain from Texas, USA, of a low-virulent *Xoo* was an exception.

enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay values (OD = 0.05 to 0.4) with *Sco-1* and therefore became part of serogroups I and II, respectively. Only two of the 70 strains did not react to *Xco-1*. A mAb-designated *Xco-T* was made to target them. This study reports on these T strains, T1 and T2, which have been characterized through plant inoculations, tests for phenotypic characteristics, and mAb and DNA probes.

Following inoculations, the T strains showed very low virulence to rice and did not cause BB symptoms on any of the differential rice cultivars after clip-inoculation. However, on swab-inoculation, we observed mild BB on IR8 and occasional streaks on DV85. Strains were re-isolated from these mild BB and BLS symptoms 14 d after inoculation.

T strains react with a genus-specific mAb for *Xanthomonas* and share some surface antigens with strains of *Xoo* and *X. o. pv. oryzicola* (*Xoor*) (BLS pathogen) (Table 1). The mAb clone 225.66.2.1, generated to a T strain, reacted with *Xoo* strains PXO86 and X1-5 and eight strains of *Xoor*. Likewise, some of their phenotypic characteristics were similar to *Xoo* while others were similar to *Xoor* (Table 2). In several characteristics, the T strains gave the same responses as the low-virulent *Xoo* strain X1-5 from Texas, USA (Table 2).

Genomic DNA of the T strains (T1, T2), a virulent *Xoo* strain from India (A3857), a low-virulent strain from the USA (X1-8), and *Xoor* strains (BLS292, BLS298, BLS303) were compared by Southern blot analysis. The four DNA probes used were the plasmids pJEL101

and pTnX1, which contain repetitive, mobile DNA elements; *pBSavrXa10*, which has a cloned avirulence gene from *Xoo*; and two *EcoRI* fragments (8.3 and 5.2 Kb, isolated from plasmid p23-44 and containing part of the *hrp* genes from *Xoo*.

The hybridization patterns of the T strains were clearly different from the patterns observed for the other strains. The pTnX1 probe did not hybridize with DNA from T1, T2, or X1-8. The cloned avirulence gene (*pBSavrXa10*) hybridized with DNA from T1 and T2, but with far fewer bands than those observed in the *Xoo* and *Xoor* strains. X1-8 did not hybridize with *pBSavrXa10*. Fewer bands of the T strains and X1-8 DNA hybridized with *hrp* genes and PJEL101 than were observed in the *Xoo* and *Xoor* strains; patterns for X1-8 and T1 and T2 clearly differed. Therefore, the genome organization of the T strains is clearly different from the Indian *Xoo* strain, the *Xoor* strains, and the USA strain (X1-8) from *Xoo*.

This study indicates that these two low-virulent bacterial strains associated with rice cannot be satisfactorily placed into current taxonomic groups using the available tests for phenotypic characteristics, molecular probes, and plant inoculations. Such strains might represent an evolutionary phase between BB and BLS pathogens of rice. Alternatively, they may belong to a completely different pathovar that has become associated with rice by chance. Although their importance is uncertain, the strains need to be monitored carefully for changes in their virulence to rice. ■

Reaction of promising rice cultivars to gall midge (GM) in coastal Karnataka, India

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GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) is the most important pest of rice in the coastal region of Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka State. We screened 55 promising cultures for resistance during 1990-92 wet seasons (WS).

Cultures were transplanted in 4-m rows spaced at 20 cm. We recorded number of tillers and silver shoots 50 d after transplanting for 10 randomly selected hills per row. Twenty entries were resistant (see table). ■